

Analysis of Performance and Commitment as Intervening of Motivation, Employee Satisfaction and Transformational Leadership at BAZNAS

Ahmad Nazir
Department of Management
Perbanas University
Jl. HR Rasuna Said No.5,Indonesia

Siti Safaria
Department of Management
Perbanas University
Jl. HR Rasuna Said No.5,Indonesia

Abstract:- Zakat is a certain portion of assets that must be paid by everyone, especially Muslims, if they have reached the specified conditions. zakat is an asset that muslim must pay from the sustenance he obtains, whether through profession, agricultural business or commerce.to overcome the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic and reduce poverty in Indonesia by making it equal between the rich and the poor. Among other things through zakat. this has a negative macroeconomic effect, there is a significant increase in the number of unemployed and poverty, so that the need for an even distribution of wealth is expected to be realized. This study analyzes the existence of commitment and performance as the influence of motivation, satisfaction and transformational leadership in the Amil Zakat in Indonesia. This research uses quantitative research methods. Primary data was collected using a questionnaire to 145 Baznas employee respondents. The analysis technique used in this study was Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with AMOS 22. The Goodness of Fit test results showed a good distribution. the results in terms of statistical calculations of motivation, transformational, and employee variable, have significant and a positive on effect in performance of organization, the result of this research showing significant both directly and indirectly use commitment of organizational as variable intervening between transformational leadership, motivation, employee satisfaction and.,

Keywords:- *Employee Satisfaction; Motivation; Organizational Commitment Organizational Performance; Transformational Leadership.*

I. INTRODUCTION

As a result of the Covid-19 pandemic, the economic setback in the socio-economic life of the people is very much felt. emergence of the impact and threat of a pandemic for the community and entrepreneurs. almost all sectors feel the impact, from the manufacturing sector, Resort and hotel, travel, and tranformation, and other sectors. This has an impact on government institutions, especially in the field of Human Resources Performance, as well as the private sector and MSMEs., to find ways to handle it. It is acknowledged that the impact of this pandemic has been felt by all sectors

starting from the micro, small and medium enterprise (MSMEs) sector.

As a result pandemic many have terminated employment or laid off their employees in several business sectors. There are also those who let go of several employees without any royalties or proper income, so that there are several sections of society who cannot get a job or a permanent income, and the economy is deteriorating. the existence of regulations to limit people's movements to prevent the spread of Covid at the beginning of 2020 which was approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia has approved the implementation of the policy making it very difficult for people to develop the economy, and private and medium-sized businesses.

As a result of the pandemic that occurred in Indonesia, there was an impact on sales, especially in the trade section of small businesses and medium businesses, showing negative figures in several fields. The existence of regulations from the government increases the inflation rate due to the large supply during the pandemic, policies that affect education, employment, restrictions on religious activities, public facilities, transportation and social activities have a huge impact on life, especially the economy in Indonesian society. various government The solution to facing the pandemic and reducing poverty in Indonesia is by sharing and distributing income, which in Islam is known as zakat. In general, zakat is everyone's obligation to spend assets in the form of goods or money provided that the assets or income obtained meet the terms and conditions and are handed over to parties in need or called muzaki.. Zakat in Islam is one of the things that must be done as a form of concern and social action to pay attention to the surrounding conditions. This obligation is mentioned repeatedly in the Qur'an along with other obligations of worship

Fig 1. Baznas Statistics 2020 (January-June)

Figure 1 shows is a report the baznas statistic in periode 2020. In general, Zakat has the concept of worship to purify the soul from stinginess, greed and selfishness as well as clearing property from other people's rights by providing some goods, prices and other positive impacts to overcome the lack of community economy for the purpose of reducing poverty, increasing economic growth, and increase purchasing power parity. Every year organizations active in zakat or the National Zakat Amil Agency (BAZNAS) provide reports on income from zakat in the form of reports to the Minister of Religion.

Zakat in its role has had very influential achievements on the economy in Indonesia, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic, this organization succeeded in collecting funds in excess of the specified target. Organizational performance is one of the things that is very necessary in achieving the vision and mission of an organization..

II. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Satisfaction of Employee

Hasibuan in his research explains the definition of emotional attitude that arises from job satisfaction, this emotional attitude has a pleasant form and likes his job,. Job satisfaction from outside the main job is employee job satisfaction that results from outside the main job, in the form of gifts or rewards from hard work, so that they can buy their needs. Handoko in his research explains the meaning of job satisfaction, namely a pleasant or unpleasant emotional state in which employees perceive their work.

B. Transformational Leadership

The ability to influence and motivate individuals to achieve organizational goals is the definition of leadership defined from research results (Gibson, et.al., 2012). Other research, namely Yukl (2010), argues that in a company the task of leadership is to influence other people to have opinions and accept tasks to be carried out effectively, the result of the quality of the leader is often considered the most important factor in the success or failure of an organization.

C. Commitment in Organization

The research before stated that commitment in an organization was interpreted in several previous studies to determine the strength of employee identity and involvement in the goals and values of the organization. Meanwhile, according to Mathis and Jackson, 2011, commitment in an organization is defined as the level of trust, loyalty and acceptance of employees towards organizational goals and the desire to remain in the organization. High commitment results in increased employee performance. Luthan in 2006 said that in organizations commitment is a form of employee loyalty to the organization and is a continuous process in which members of the organization express their concern for the organization. If an employee has high organizational commitment, achieving organizational goals is important for him, on the other hand, if an employee has low organizational commitment, his attention is low and tends to only prioritize personal interests.

D. Organizational Performance

Abdullah and Arisanti, in their research, revealed that work performance and the process of implementing organizational goals to be achieved are in the form of organizational performance, which is the level of work success achieved from an activity in the organization in a certain period which is oriented towards the organization's vision and mission, which is the result of performance. Organizations can because the form of performance can also be a measurement of business achievements that have been carried out which can be measured with indicators. Gibson in his research also revealed that performance can also be considered as a contribution to organizational results in terms of the resources expended so that it can be stated that performance is the result achieved from the behavior of the members of the organization itself.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This research tests the relationship between variables using the Structural Equation Model (SEM), because the concepts of research and SEM both have a cause and effect relationship. Endogenous or variable Y is the definition of the dependent variable while the results are determined regularly by the independent or exogenous variable = the results of SEM give the results of the coefficients between related variables.

This study uses several indices such as the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Adjusted Goodness of Fit (AGFI), Chi-Square, Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) and Degrees of Freedom Divided Minimum Sample Difference Function (CMIN/DF).

Fig 2. Result SEM Model

The result of figure 2 is :

- The probability declared good fit because the value is $0.342 > 0.05$
- CMIN/DF declared good fit. because is the value is $1.114 < 2.00$
- GFI declared good fit because value is $0.904 > 0.90$,
- The AGFI declared good fit because value is $0.902, > 0.90$
- TLI declared good fit because value is $0.901 > 0.90$
- CFI declared good fit because value is $0.911 > 0.90$,

The regression weight result is;

- Motivation is the main point to cause a member of the organization to be willing and willing to exert their abilities and performance to achieve the goals and objectives of the organization that have been set, so that it can be concluded that motivation has a significant positive effect on organizational performance
- Satisfaction is affected by the commitment of each employee so that it can be concluded that employee satisfaction has a significant positive effect on Organizational Commitment at the National Amil Zakat Agency (BAZNAS).
- Leadership is an ability. The quality of a leader is often considered the most important factor in the success or failure of an organization in terms of the commitment of each employee or organization, so it can be concluded that Transformational Leadership has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment at the National Amil Zakat Agency (BAZNAS),
- Motivation is a desire within a person that causes that person to take action. Someone takes an action to achieve a goal, the higher the motivation, the higher the performance, so that it can be concluded that motivation has a significant positive effect on performance at the National Amil Zakat Agency (BAZNAS),
- Leaders must determine what employees must do in order to achieve their own or organizational goals and help employees gain confidence in carrying out these tasks, so that it can be concluded that Transformational Leadership has a significant positive effect on performance at the National Amil Zakat Agency (BAZNAS),

- job satisfaction is a general attitude which is the result of several specific attitudes towards work factors, so it can be concluded that employee satisfaction has a significant positive effect on performance at the National Amil Zakat Agency (BAZNAS),
- Employees have high organizational commitment, achieving organizational performance goals is important, so that the conclusion is that commitment has a significant positive effect on performance at the National Amil Zakat Agency (BAZNAS).
- organizational commitment as an attitude that reflects employee loyalty to the organization to support, so it can be concluded that commitment has a significant positive effect on performance at the National Amil Zakat Agency (BAZNAS), with loyalty to organizational performance success and sustainable progress
- the influence of leaders who increase individual and group self-confidence, increase awareness and interest in groups and organizations, and try to move subordinates' attention to achievement and existence development, so that it can be concluded that Transformational Leadership has a significant positive effect on employee satisfaction at the National Amil Zakat Agency (National Amil Zakat Agency). BAZNAS),

IV. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this research is that motivation, transformational leadership and commitment are strengths possessed by members of the Baznas organization to carry out their duties as zakat officers. with this, many users have satisfaction because their right to pay zakat has been fulfilled, as well as satisfaction within their group, this is due to the existence of an integrated system run by leaders who create individual and group self-confidence, raise awareness of the role of zakat, thereby giving rise to interest of several other organizations to participate in zakat

REFERENCES

- [1]. Bass, B.M. (1997). The Transactional-Transformational Leadership
- [2]. Ellitan, L. (2002), Praktik-praktik Pengelolaan Sumber Daya Manusia dan Keunggulan Kompetitif Berkelanjutan, Vol.4 : 68
- [3]. Ferdinand, A. (2014). Metode Penelitian Manajemen. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [4]. Gibson, et.al. (2012). Organizations (Behavior, Structure, Processes), Fourteenth Edition. USA: McGrow Hill.
- [5]. Ghozali, I. (2013). Model Persamaan Struktural : Konsep dan Aplikasi dengan Program AMOS 21.0. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [6]. Ghozali, I. (2011). Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program IBM SPSS 19. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [7]. Gomes, F. Cardoso, (2003). Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Cetakan Kedua, Penerbit Andi Offset, Yogyakarta,.

- [8]. Habibur Rahman, Md, Mst. Rinu Fatema and Md. Hazrat Ali., (2019), Impact of Motivation and Job Satisfaction on Employee's Performance: An Empirical Study, *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, Vol. 10(4): pp. 1-10
- [9]. Hafidhuddin, Didin. (2006). Analisis Efektifitas Promosi Lembaga Amil Zakat Dalam Penghimpunan Zakat Bagi Peningkatan Kesejahteraan Keluarga Dhuafa: Studi Kasus Lembaga Amil Zakat Dompot Dhuafa Republika. *Media Gizi & Keluarga*, Juli 2006, 30(1): 100-109.
- [10]. Hair, J.F. et.al. (2014). *Multivariate Data Analysis*, Seventh Edition. USA: Pearson Education, Inc.
- [11]. Handoko, Hani T. (2011). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Yogyakarta : BPFE Yogyakarta.
- [12]. Handoko, T.Hani. (2000). *Manajemen Personalia dan Sumber Daya Manusia*. Edisi ke 2, Yogyakarta: BPFE
- [13]. Hardiyansyah. (2011). *Kualitas Pelayanan Publik Konsep, Dimensi, Indikator, dan Implementasi*. Yogyakarta: Gava Media.
- [14]. Hasibuan, Malayu. (2013). *MSDM*. Jakarta : Bumi Aksara
- [15]. Ismawanto, Setianegara dan Rahmani (2020) . Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan Dan Kinerja Karyawan Frontliner Terhadap Kepuasan Nasabah PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero), Tbk Kantor Cabang Balikpapan Sudirman Unit Klandasan. *Jurnal Bisnis & Kewirausahaan*, Volume 16, No.1 hal 1-11
- [16]. Juniari, NKE, Riana, IG, Subudi M. (2015), Pengaruh Motivasi Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja dan Kinerja Pegawai Negeri Sipil (PNS) di Sekolah Tinggi Pariwisata Nusa Dua Bali, *E-Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Udayana*, Vol. 11 No. 4, Hal. 823-840
- [17]. Jonathan Sarwono (2012) *Path Analysis dengan SPSS : Teori, Aplikasi, Prosedur Analisa untuk Riset Skripsi, Tesis dan Disertasi*, Jakarta: Elex Media Komputindo Kompas Gramedia.
- [18]. J.Tatilu, V.P.K Lengkong, G. Sendow, *Kepemimpinan Transaksional, Transformasional, Servant Leadership Pengaruhnya Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Sinar Galesong Pratama Manado* (2014), *Jurnal EMBA*, Vol.2 No.1, Hal. 295-304
- [19]. Kaplan, R.S. (2001). *Strategic Performance Measurement and Management in Nonprofit Organizations*. *Journal of Nonprofit Management and Leadership*. Vol.10 No.3 hal. 353-370.
- [20]. Kurtz Clow. (1998). *Service Marketing*. Will & Sons Inc, USA.
- [21]. Kedsuda Limsila and Stephen O. Ogunlana, (2008), Performance and leadership outcome correlates of leadership styles and subordinate commitment, *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, Vol. 15 No. 2, pp. 164-184
- [22]. Kertiriasih NNR, Sujana IW, Suardika IN, (2018), The Effect of Leadership Style to Job Satisfaction, Employee Engagement and Employee Performance(Study at PT. Interbat, Bali, Nusra, and Ambon), *International Journal of Contemporary Research and Review*, Vol. 09 Issue. 03 Page no: ME 20592-20600
- [23]. Kotler P. (2000). *Marketing Management; Analysis, Planning, Implementation and Control*. Prentice-Hall. Inc.
- [24]. Lanyon, R.I. and Leonard, D.G. (1997). *Personality Assessment*. New York: John Wiley& Sons, Inc.
- [25]. Limsila,K and Ogunlana,SO.(2008) Performance and leadership outcome correlates of leadership styles and subordinate commitment, *Journal Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, Vol. 15 No. 2, pp. 164-184
- [26]. Luthans, Fred. (2005). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Edisi 10. Dialihbahasakan Oleh Vivin Andhika
- [27]. Mangkunegara, A.P, (2009). *Evaluasi Kinerja Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bandung:PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- [28]. Mangkuprawira, Syafri. (2007). *Manajemen Mutu Sumber Daya Manusia*. Bogor : Gali,Indonesia.
- [29]. Masa'deh, R. Obeidat, BY. dan Tarhini A. (2016). A Jordanian Empirical Study Of The Associations Among Transformational Leadership, Transactional Leadership, Knowledge Sharing, Job Performance, And Firm Performance A Structural Equation Modelling Approach. *Journal of Management Development*. Vol. 35 No.5 hal 681-705.
- [30]. Muhammad, Sam Adamu, Saad Ram Al-Jaffri. (2016). Moderating Effect of Attitude toward Zakat Payment on the Relationship between Moral Reasoning and Intention to Pay Zakat. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences* 219:520-52
- [31]. Permono, Sjechul Hadi. (2005). *Formula Zakat Menuju Kesejahteraan Sosial*. Surabaya: CV Aulia Surabaya
- [32]. Raymond, P.C., Hatane, S., dan J. Hutabarat. (2015). Analisis Kualitas Sumber Daya Manusia, Kualitas Pelayanan, Kinerja Organisasi, Kepercayaan Masyarakat Dan Kepuasan Masyarakat (Studi Kasus: Dinas Kependudukan Dan Catatan Sipil Kabupaten Nabire). *Jurnal Teknologi dan Manajemen Industri*. Vol. 1 No. 1 hal 1-8
- [33]. Robbins, S.P.,Timothy A.Judge. (2015). *Perilaku Organisasi*. Edisi 16. Jakarta : Salemba Empat.
- [34]. Robbins, S.P. and Mary Coulter. (1996). *Management*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall, Inc.
- [35]. Robbins Stephen P., (2001).*Organizational Behavior (Terjemahan) Jilid 1*, Edisi Kedelapan, PT. Bhuana Ilmu Populer, Jakarta
- [36]. Santosa, B., Dari "Brain Drain" ke "Brain Gain". *Kompas* 2-5-2014,(6).
- [37]. Sastra Tamami., (2015). Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Dan Motivasi Terhadap Kualitas Pelayanan Dan Kinerja Pegawai (Studi Kasus Sekretariat DPRD Kota Batam). *Dosen Tetap Prodi Manajemen FE UNRIKA Batam*.
- [38]. Susilo Martoyo, (1992), *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*, Edisi ke 2, (1992), BPFE UGM, Yogyakarta.
- [39]. Schiff, A dan M. Hoffman. (1996). An Exploration of the use of financial and Non-financial Measurement of Performance by Executive in a Service Organization. *Behavioral in Accounting Research*. Fal., 123-146
- [40]. Soedjono. (2005). Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi Terhadap Kinerja Organisasi dan Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan pada Terminal Penumpang Umum di Surabaya. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Kewirausahaan*. Vol. 7 No.1 hal. 22-47.

- [41]. Spector, P.E. (2006). *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*. New York: John Wiley.
- [42]. Sulaiman, et.al. (2014). Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan dan Gaya Komunikasi terhadap Kinerja Pegawai serta Dampaknya pada Kinerja Sekretariat Daerah Kabupaten Pidie Jaya. *Jurnal Manajemen Pascasarjana Universitas Syiah Kuala*. Vol.3 No.2 hal. 78-84.
- [43]. Syahrullah, Maria Ulfah. (2016). Response of Indonesian Academicians toward Factors Influencing the Payment of Zakat on Employment Income. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*. Vol.6, No.10, 87-94
- [44]. Tatilu, James, Victor P.K Lengkong, and Greis M. Sendow, (2014), *Kepemimpinan Transaksional, Transformasional, Servant Leadership Pengaruhnya Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Sinar Galesong Pratama Manado*, *Jurnal EMBA*, Vol.2 No.1, Hal. 295-304
- [45]. Taurisa, C.M. dan Ratnawati, I. (2012). Analisis Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi dan Kepuasan Kerja terhadap Komitmen Organisasional dalam Meningkatkan Kinerja Karyawan (Studi pada PT. Sido Muncul Kaligawe Semarang). *Jurnal Bisnis dan Ekonomi*. Vol.19 No.2 hal. 170-187.
- [46]. Wibowo. (2014). *Manajemen Kinerja*, Cetakan keempat. Jakarta :PT. RAJAGRAFINDOPERSADA, Jakarta.
- [47]. Widodo, P. dan Kamilah, A. (2011). Hubungan Antara Budaya Organisasi, Komitmen Organisasi dan Locus Of Control terhadap Kinerja Manajemen. *Jurnal Agribisnis dan Pengembangan Wilayah*. Vol.2 No.2 hal. 51-64.
- [48]. Wulandary, T, Syamsun M, Dirjosuparto, S. (2017), Pengaruh Adaptabilitas Budaya Organisasi Dan Motivasi Terhadap Komitmen Karyawan Pada Organisasi PT Krakatau Steel TBK, *Jurnal Aplikasi Bisnis dan Manajemen*, Vol. 3 No. 2, hal 196-207
- [49]. Woolfolk, Anita E. (1995). *Educational Psychology*. Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
- [50]. Yavirach, Natepanna Assoc. Prof., (2012). The Impact Of Transformational And Transactional Leadership To Subordinate's Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment Affect To Team Effectiveness. Faculty of Business Administration Rajamangala University of Technology, Thanyburi, Thailand, electronic copy available at: <http://ssrn.com/abstract=2159035>
- [51]. Yukl, G. (2010). *Leadership in Organization*, Seventh Edition. USA: Pearson Education, Inc.
- [52]. Yuwono, Shekar Purwanti, Th Arie P & Winong Rosari. (2008). *Perilaku Organisasional*. Yogyakarta : Andi.
- [53]. Zeithmal, V.A.P. dan Berry, L.L.A. (1985). Conceptual Model of Service Quality and Its Implications for Future Research. *Journal of Marketing*, XV(1), pp.41-50